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ФАН ВА ТАЪЛИМ**

**ҚАРАҚАЛПАҚСТАНДА
ИЛИМ ҲӘМ ТӘЛИМ**

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В КАРАКАЛПАКСТАНЕ**

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IRRIGATION PERIODS, NUMBER, SYSTEM AND SEASONAL IRRIGATION NORMS OF CORN VARIETIES IN CONDITIONS OF MEADOW-ALLUVIAL SOILS

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CONCLUSION. It can be concluded from the information obtained on irrigation procedures of corn varieties in relation to soil moisture field capacity in the conditions of meadow-alluvial soils that in the 60-60-60% irrigation system, the main crop was irrigated once during budding-flowering, and the repeated crop was not irrigated. Irrigation method 70-70-60% required irrigation in 1-2-0 system, one-time irrigation rate was in the range of 972-1047 m³/ha, and seasonal irrigation rate was equal to 3050; 2974; 2978 m³/ha. In the irrigation order of 80-80-60% soil moisture, the main crop was irrigated 5 times in the 1-4-0 system, the seasonal irrigation rate was 3431; 3287; 3407 m³/ha. In the experiment, according to the analysis of the biometric properties of corn varieties and the state of soil reclamation, taking into account that the best indicator was recorded in the irrigation regime, for this soil and climate, it is acceptable to irrigate corn varieties in the order of 70-70-60%, seasonal irrigation in the 1-2-0 system at the rate of 3050-2978 m³/ha.

Keywords: meadow-alluvial soils, irrigation methods, irrigation system, standard corn varieties, main crop, repeated crop.

Abstract. In the article, the results of the study on determining optimal irrigation procedures for "Uzbekistan-601 ESV", "Karasuv-350 AMV" and "Uzbekistan-300 MV" varieties of corn cultivated as a main and repeated crop in the conditions of moderately saline, meadow-alluvial soils of the southern Aral Sea region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan are presented.

Introduction. The main purpose of irrigation is to deliver the necessary moisture in the soil for agricultural crops, to ensure and manage the water, food, air temperature regimes of the soil necessary for the crops, as well as the optimal biological conditions in the irrigated areas.

Irrigation rate is the water rate (m³/ha) given to 1 ha irrigated area for one-time irrigation of agricultural crops.

Irrigation standards for cultivated crops should ensure that the active layer of the soil provides the moisture used by the plant in the layer where 90% of the plant's roots are located.

Corn grows slowly in the first period (germination). From the fertilization period, the development of corn is intensive, depending on the variety. Daily growth is 8-10 cm and more. Blue mass accumulates a lot, a yield is formed. During this period, soil moisture should not be less than 70-75% [1].

B.S. Mambetnazarov [2]'s long-term scientific research in the conditions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan shows that the use of groundwater by corn is much less than that of cotton and alfalfa, and the efficiency of use is 30-35% when the groundwater is 2-3 m deep, and when it is 1-2 m, it reaches 40-45%. Therefore, according to the author, soil moisture is also important in such lands.

According to V. I. Kuznetsov [3], the timing of irrigation should be based on weather conditions. For the calculated layer 0.4 m irrigation depth, it is necessary to irrigate 9 times in average wet years, and 2 times to increase the wetting depth to 0.8 m in dry years. According to him, the depth of the moistened soil layer and the stage of plant development have a decisive influence on the amount of water consumption during the harvesting process of corn. The main part of the water balance in the total water consumption is irrigation water. In the version with a moisture depth of 0.4 - 0.8 m, its share varies from 50 to 73.3%. This indicator decreases when the soil layer is wetted by 0.4 m (52.7 %) and increases as the depth of subsidence increases by 0.8 (59.9 %).

Also, in the research of M.S.Bhuiyan, M.S.R.Bhuiyan, T.P.Tiwari, M.A.Rahaman, S.K.Bhowal, R. Uddin and S.K.Paul [4], 3 different irrigations of hybrid corn varieties were selected

at 25, 50 and 75 days intervals and reported that the best performance was observed in BARI hybrid corn variety.

According to Dilip Chenoy [5], corn is considered as a potential crop for India to double the farmer's income. That is why agrotechnics of corn care (plowing, irrigation, feeding, etc.) are important in these conditions.

Therefore, it is one of the important tasks to determine the optimal irrigation procedures for corn as the main and repeated crop in different soil-climatic conditions, including moderately saline, meadow-alluvial soils of the southern Aral region.

Research methods. The researches were conducted in the experimental farm of the Karakalpakstan Agricultural Scientific Research Institute in 2020-2022 as the main and repeated crops of corn varieties "Uzbekistan-601 ESV", "Karasuv-350 AMV" and "Uzbekistan-300 MV". Before irrigation, each variety was irrigated in 60-60-60, 70-70-60 and 80-80-60% irrigation regimes compared to field capacity, and the number, rate and system of irrigation were studied. The analyzes were carried out on the basis of methodological guidelines "Methods for conducting field experiments" [6].

Corn irrigation was carried out in three periods. The first period is the germination period, the second period is the fruiting period, and the third period is the grain ripening period.

The experiment was carried out in 9 variants in the main and repeated crops. The area of each plot is 480 m² (row length 50 m, width 8 rows 0.6x8=480 m²), from which 240 m² is taken into account. The experiment was in 3 replications, and all variants were systematically placed in the same tier.

Analysis and results. Corn gets the moisture it needs (nutrients) from the active layer of the soil. Irrigations with high or low irrigation rates have different effects on corn. Therefore, it is appropriate to determine scientifically based irrigation periods, number, system, duration and seasonal irrigation norms.

We will analyze the obtained data in the example of 2022.

In the experimental fields, the number of irrigations, durations, annual and seasonal irrigation norms of the Uzbekistan 601 ESV, Karasuv 350 AMV and Uzbekistan 300 MV corn varieties differed from each other. According to the data obtained in field experiments, soil moisture before irrigation of Uzbekistan 601 ESV, Karasuv 350 AMV varieties planted as the main crop was carried out once according to the irrigation order 60-60-60% compared to field capacity, in options 1, 2 and 3 at 0-1-0 system and the irrigation rate was 1301, 1280, 1310 m³/ha. In options 4, 5 and 6, soil moisture before irrigation was 70-70-60% compared to field capacity, irrigation was required in the 1-2-0 system, the rate of one-time irrigation was in the range of 972-1047 m³/ha, and the rate of seasonal irrigation was equal to 3050; 2974; 2978 m³/ha. The interval between irrigations corresponded to the interval of 25-28 days. The complete data obtained are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

On the irrigation rate of 80-80-60 % soil moisture relative to field capacity Uzbekistan 601 ESV, Karasuv 350 AMV and Uzbekistan 300 MV corn varieties was irrigated in the 1-4-0 system. Periodic irrigation rate was in the range of 630-740 m³/ha and seasonal irrigation rate was 3431; 3287; 3407 m³/ha.

As a repeated crop, irrigation was not required in options 1, 2 and 3, where the soil moisture was set at 60% in all periods compared to field capacity, in the experiments conducted to determine the irrigation norms, system, and seasonal irrigation norms of varieties of corn Uzbekistan 601 ESV, Karasuv 350 AMV and Uzbekistan 300 MV.

Re-planted corn cultivars required a single irrigation when the soil moisture was 70-70-60% relative to field capacity. The rate of one-time and seasonal irrigation was 1008; 1070; 1084 m³/ha, respectively.

Re-planted Uzbekistan 601 ESV, Karasuv 350 AMV and Uzbekistan 300 MV corn varieties were irrigated 2 times in the 1-1-0 system in options 7, 8 and 9 with soil moisture of 80-80-60% according to field capacity. It was found that the daily irrigation rate was around 672-750 m³/ha and the seasonal irrigation rate was 1452; 1443; 1421 m³/ha.

Table 1.
Irrigation regimes of corn varieties grown as main crops on meadow-alluvial soils,
(2022)

V er · n	Irrigation procedures in relation to field capacity, %	Corn varieties	Indicators	number of irrigation					Seasonal irrigation rate, m ³ /ha	Irrigation system
				1	2	3	4	5		
1	60-60-60	Uzbekistan 601 ESV	Irrigation period, date	6.07					1301	0-1-0
			Irrigation interval, date							
			Irrigation rate, m ³ /ha	1301						
2	60-60-60	Karasuv 350 AMV	Irrigation period, date	3.07					1280	0-1-0
			Irrigation interval, date							
			Irrigation rate, m ³ /ha	1280						
3	60-60-60	Uzbekistan 300 MW	Irrigation period, date	5.07					1310	0-1-0
			Irrigation interval, date							
			Irrigation rate, m ³ /ha	1310						
4	70-70-60	Uzbekistan 601 ESV	Irrigation period, date	13.06	11.07	14.08			3050	1-2-0
			Irrigation interval, date	28	35					
			Irrigation rate, m ³ /ha	972	1047	1031				
5	70-70-60	Karasuv 350 AMV	Irrigation period, date	11.06	10.07	15.08			2974	1-2-0
			Irrigation interval, date	29	35					
			Irrigation rate, m ³ /ha	986	972	1016				
6	70-70-60	Uzbekistan 300 MW	Irrigation period, date	9.06	11.07	16.08			2978	1-2-0
			Irrigation interval, date	32	35					
			Irrigation rate, m ³ /ha	986	990	1002				
7	80-80-60	Uzbekistan 601 ESV	Irrigation period, date	29.05	19.06	10.07	1.08	25.08	3431	1-4-0
			Irrigation interval, date	21	21	22	24			
			Irrigation rate, m ³ /ha	630	687	710	687	717		
8	80-80-80	Karasuv 350 AMV	Irrigation period, date	28.05	17.06	11.07	3.08	26.08	3287	1-4-0
			Irrigation interval, date	20	24	22	23			
			Irrigation rate, m ³ /ha	642	642	650	673	680		

9	80-80-80	Uzbekistan 300 MW	Irrigation period, date	30.05	18.06	10.07	30.07	20.08	3407	1-4-0
			Irrigation interval, date	19	22	20	21			
			Irrigation rate, m ³ /ha	702	673	642	650	740		

Table 2.
Irrigation regimes of corn varieties planted as a repeated crop on meadow-alluvial soils, (2022)

Ver. n	Irrigation procedures in relation to field capacity, %	Corn varieties	Indicators	number of irrigation					Seasonal irrigation rate, m ³ /ha	Irrigation system
				1	2	3	4	5		
1	60-60-60	Uzbekistan 601 ESV	Irrigation period, date						1008	0-0-0
			Irrigation interval, date							
			Irrigation rate, m ³ /ha							
2	60-60-60	Karasuv 350 AMV	Irrigation period, date						1070	0-0-0
			Irrigation interval, date							
			Irrigation rate, m ³ /ha							
3	60-60-60	Uzbekistan 300 MW	Irrigation period, date						1084	0-0-0
			Irrigation interval, date							
			Irrigation rate, m ³ /ha							
4	70-70-60	Uzbekistan 601 ESV	Irrigation period, date	25.07					1452	0-1-0
			Irrigation interval, date							
			Irrigation rate, m ³ /ha	1008						
5	70-70-60	Karasuv 350 AMV	Irrigation period, date	23.07					1443	0-1-0
			Irrigation interval, date							
			Irrigation rate, m ³ /ha	1070						
6	70-70-60	Uzbekistan 300 MW	Irrigation period, date	21.07					1421	0-1-0
			Irrigation interval, date							
			Irrigation rate, m ³ /ha	1084						
7	80-80-60	Uzbekistan 601 ESV	Irrigation period, date	17.07	20.08				1443	1-1-0
			Irrigation interval, date	33						
			Irrigation rate, m ³ /ha	702	750					
8	80-80-80	Karasuv 350 AMV	Irrigation period, date	19.07	21.08				1421	1-1-0
			Irrigation interval, date	32						
			Irrigation rate, m ³ /ha	733	710					
9	80-80-80	Uzbekistan 300 MW	Irrigation period, date	16.07	15.08				1421	1-1-0

			Irrigation interval, date	29					
			Irrigation rate, m ³ /ha	749	672				

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Rezyume: *Maqolada Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasi janubiy orol bo'yi hududi o'rtacha sho'rlangan, o'tloqi-allyuvial tuproqlari sharoitida asosiy va takroriy ekin sifatida parvarishlangan makkajo'xorining “O'zbekiston-601 ESV”, “Karasuv-350 AMV” va “O'zbekiston-300 MV” navlarini maqbul sug'orish tartiblarini aniqlash bo'yicha tadqiqot natijalari keltirilgan.*

Резюме: *В статье приведены результаты исследования по определению оптимальных режимов орошения сортов кукурузы «Узбекистан-601 ЭСВ», «Карасув-350 АМВ» и «Узбекистан-300 МВ», возделываемых в качестве основной и повторной культуры, в условиях среднесоленых, лугово-аллювиальных почв южного Приаралья Республики Каракалпакстан.*

Kalit so'zlar: *o'tloqi-allyuvial tuproqlar, sug'orish tartiblari, sug'orish tizimi, me'yor makkajo'xori navlari, asosiy ekin, takroriy ekin.*

Ключевые слова: *лугово-аллювиальные почвы, способы орошения, оросительная система, стандартные сорта кукурузы, основная культура, повторная культура.*